

ABSTRACT

An Information-Theoretic Measure for Pattern Similarity in Analog WafermapsBernhard C. Geiger^{1,*}, Stefan Schrunner^{2,*}, Roman Kern^{1,3}¹ Know-Center GmbH, Graz, AT² KAI Kompetenzzentrum Automobil- und Industrieelektronik GmbH, Villach, AT³ Graz University of Technology, Graz, AT

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Motivation

The development of automated tools for data analysis is a growing need in semiconductor manufacturing. For this purpose, especially wafer test data carry a high potential as they allow the expert to draw conclusions on both product performance, as well as production process deviations. The latter are assumed to be identifiable by spatial patterns on wafermaps. The target of this work is to propose a system that judges the similarities between wafermaps regarding the depicted process pattern in an automated way. For this purpose, we propose a similarity measure to perform a pairwise comparison of wafermaps based on extracted, high-dimensional features.

Description

Suppose that each wafermap consists of n devices which are characterized by numerical features taking values in a finite set. We can thus represent each wafermap by a normalized histogram of these numerical features (cf. Santos et al., 2018, Sec. III.A), which can be interpreted as an empirical discrete probability distribution. Given that a pattern is sufficiently captured by these features, two wafermaps W_1 and W_2 are assumed to be similar to the extent to which their empirical probability distributions p_1 and p_2 are computed to be similar. We measure the similarity between discrete probability distributions (thus between wafermaps) using the **Jensen-Shannon divergence (JSD)** (Lin, 1991)

$$JSD(W_1, W_2) := H\left(\frac{p_1 + p_2}{2}\right) - 0.5H(p_1) - 0.5H(p_2),$$

where $H(p)$ is the entropy of the discrete distribution p (Cover & Thomas, 1991). The JSD is non-negative, where small values indicate that the two wafermaps are similar.

To meaningfully employ JSD as a measure of pattern similarity, one has to ensure that the empirical probability distribution of the device features in some sense represents the pattern. We utilize the feature extraction scheme proposed in (Santos et al., 2018) for analog wafermaps: In the first step, the wafer W is segmented into regions of interest R . Each device is represented by a feature, restricted to these regions, obtained by comparing its measurement value to those of its neighbors. Finally, the empirical probability distribution of

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the wafer W is obtained by normalizing the histogram of these feature values by the number of devices $|R|$ on the region of interest.

We make two more simplifications: First, we assume that outside the regions of interest, the empirical distribution of the extracted feature values is the same for all wafers. Second, we assume that the distributions within the region of interest are vastly different from the distribution outside the regions of interest. Under these assumptions, it can be shown that for two wafermaps W_1 and W_2 with regions of interest R_1 and R_2 with empirical distributions r_1 and r_2 , above equation is replaced by (Geiger, 2018, Obs. 4)

$$JSD(W_1, W_2) = \frac{|R_1|+|R_2|}{2n} H\left(\frac{|R_1|r_1+|R_2|r_2}{|R_1|+|R_2|}\right) - \frac{|R_1|}{2n} H(r_1) - \frac{|R_2|}{2n} H(r_2) + JSD(|R_1|, |R_2|),$$

where the last term is the JSD between two Bernoulli distributions with parameters R_1/n and R_2/n , respectively. This simplification has the advantage that its computation requires only the size of the regions of interest and the distributions *inside these regions*, but not the distributions on the entire wafer. It therefore fits nicely into the feature extraction pipeline proposed in (Santos et al., 2018, Sec. III.A).

Innovation

The innovation in this work is the proposal of a similarity measure to compare analog wafermaps based on process patterns. Utilizing a previously proposed feature extraction pipeline, which was shown to preserve information about patterns, we obtain an empirical distribution as a representative for each wafermap. The JSD is justified as a similarity measure because of its role in bounding classification problems (Lin, 1991, Th. 4 & 5) and at the same time having desirable properties for the analysis of analog wafermaps: It allows distinguishing wafermaps with the same pattern occurring in different sizes (Geiger, 2018, Obs. 3), and its expression simplifies, if the measurements in the “normal” wafermap region differ significantly from those in the regions of interest (Geiger, 2018, Obs. 4).

Results

To practically illustrate the performance of our proposed similarity measure, we conducted an experiment with a synthetic wafer test dataset comprised of five commonly occurring process patterns, see Fig. 1. We utilized the dataset as well as the feature extraction pipeline from (Santos et al., 2018, Sec. III.A), with the exception that the 512-dimensional histograms were directly used, instead of performing a dimensionality reduction based on principal component analysis. The wafermaps were directly clustered based on these empiric distributions. To this end, we performed hierarchical agglomerative clustering using the simplified JSD as a similarity measure.

We grouped the wafermaps from the training dataset into 6, 11 and 16 clusters by hierarchical clustering. In each case, the cluster assignments of the wafermaps are compared to their ground truth via confusion matrices. The results are presented in Tab. 1.

One can observe that the proposed similarity measure yields good clustering results for the wafer test dataset. The achieved results show that 4 out of the 5 simulated wafer patterns could be discriminated in an accurate way. Note, however, that the proposed similarity

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measure can only discriminate patterns if the corresponding extracted features are distinct. For example, pattern 3 is a gradient over the entire wafer, where the gradient can assume one out of eight different directions. The feature extraction method proposed in (Santos et al., 2018, Sec. III.A) yields features that are different for these direction, effectively split these wafermaps into multiple subclusters (see also (Santos et al., 2018, Fig. 1). All other patterns are correctly identified, given a sufficiently large number of clusters. As such, we believe our proposed similarity measure fulfills both, the theoretical and practical requirements, to sufficiently well represent the link between the similarity of production-critical patterns and their resulting empirical distributions.

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(a) Pattern 1 (b) Pattern 2 (c) Pattern 3 (d) Pattern 4 (e) Pattern 5

Fig. 1: Five types of spatial patterns are simulated as prototypes for process pattern recognition. Pattern 1 depicts a strong area at the border of the wafer, Pattern 2 consists of a spot at arbitrary position on the wafer. Pattern 3 is a gradient with variable direction, while Pattern 4 is defined by two spots on opposite sides of the wafer. Pattern 5 is a crescent-shaped area on the right side of the

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Cluster	Pattern				
	1	2	3	4	5
1	200	200		200	200
2			51		
3			24		
4			83		
5			21		
6			21		

(a) 5 clusters

Cluster	Pattern				
	1	2	3	4	5
1	200			200	
2		200			
3			27		
4			24		
5			24		
6			28		
7			21		
8			25		
9			21		
10			30		
11					200

(b) 11 clusters

Cluster	Pattern				
	1	2	3	4	5
1	200				
2		200			
3			27		
4			15		
5			10		
6			28		
7			21		
8			13		
9			9		
10			21		
11			14		
12			12		
13			14		
14			16		
15				200	
16					200

(c) 16 clusters

Tab. 1: Confusion matrices of clustering results using the presented similarity measure, compared to the ground truth of the wafermaps (= real underlying pattern). The number of clusters is limited to 6 clusters (a), 11 clusters (b) or 16 clusters (c). The dataset contains 5 distinct patterns, each shown on 200 wafermaps in the test dataset. In general, patterns 1, 2, 4 and 5 can be perfectly